

A REPAIR METHOD OF DELAMINATED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES USING MICRO BOLTS

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Keywords: Composite repair, Delamination, Recovery, Microbolt

ABSTRACT

A new method using micro bolt to repair delaminated composite laminate is proposed. To confirm the tensile strength of the repaired laminate, tensile tests were performed on with various hole sizes. Compression test is also performed to compare the buckling load of repaired specimen and unrepaired. In the test results, proposed repair method using micro bolts showed better results than scarf patch method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon-epoxy composites have been used in various fields due to their excellent mechanical properties. When the composite structures are applied to a certain kind of primary structure, they could be able to endure the damages caused by impact, fatigue and the other operation conditions. Because composite structures are generally manufactured by laminating thin plies, they have weak properties in thickness direction than in-plane properties. Because of the weak properties in the thickness direction, delamination is the most common failure mode of the laminated composites[1]. The scarf patch-repair method is a useful repair method for the composite structures. To repair the composite structures using scarf patch, however, lots of time and costs are required[2]. Furthermore, it is difficult to repair the structures with curvature. In this paper, a new repair method is suggested to repair the delaminated composite structures. This is a repair method using micro bolts. Although making a hole causes strength degradation, the effect of small holes on the strength of laminate are not much serious. In this study, to prove the excellence of this method, two types of test were conducted.

2 TEST AND CONCLUSION

One was the compression test to compare the buckling load of repaired specimen with those of the damaged and undamaged specimens. Nine 0.6 mm bolts were used for each repaired specimen. The average buckling load of undamaged specimens is 22.4 kN. Buckling load recovery rate of repaired and unrepaired specimens is 92% and 74%, respectively. The open hole specimens with different diameters were also tested to examine the effect of hole size on the laminate strength[3]. The failure strength was calculated based on net-section area. No-hole specimen was tested to get the reference data as well the average failure strength of it was 879.8 MPa. The failure strength recovery rates of the specimens with the hole diameters of 0.6, 1.0, 3.0, and 6.0 mm were 92, 86, 72, and 70% respectively. From the results, we could expect that if the smaller hole than 0.6 mm diameter can be fabricated, it could result in the higher strength that is almost same as the strength of undamaged structures. In terms of the weight, proposed repair method using micro bolts showed better results than scarf patch method.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by the Human Resource Training Program for Regional Innovation and Creativity through the Ministry of Education and National Research Foundation of Korea (2015H1C1A1035655). And it was supported by the Technology Innovation Program (or Industrial Strategic Technology Development Program(10077320, Development of 700bar hydrogen storage vessel manufacturing technology for FCEV using high speed filament winding method) funded By the Ministry of Trade, Industry & Energy(MOTIE, Korea)

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